

Rectum cancer championship phase V4

ID: 0c709381-69fd-44fd-8417-26e1a181c1a9

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 518

Subjects count: 346

Age range: Between 28 years and 89 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): ABDOMEN, RECTUM, PELVIS, PROSTATE, BLADDER, ARM, ABDOMENPELVIS, PANCREAS, CANALANAL, UTERUS, PELVISLOWEREXTR, PENIS, Unknown

Modality: MR